

PREPARING FUTURE PROFESSIONALS FOR INTELLECTUAL EDUCATION**Torakulov X.A.**

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Abstract. *This article examines a number of achievements and advantages in teaching according to the educational paradigm, and the intellectual system of acquiring knowledge.*

Keywords: *intellectual, society, state, educational system, process, science, technology.*

ПОДГОТОВКА БУДУЩИХ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ К ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОМУ ОБРАЗОВАНИЮ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается ряд достижений и преимуществ в обучении по образовательной парадигме и интеллектуальной системе получения знаний.*

Ключевые слова: *интеллектуал, общество, государство, система образования, процесс, наука, технология.*

It is known that the level of intellectuality of the society and the state is determined by the achievements of science, technology and technology created by the generation of intellectual potential in that society and the state, as well as the implementation of pedagogical innovations based on them. If we pay attention to today's development in this regard, the achievements of science and technology are penetrating deeply into all spheres of human activity. As a result, "smart" techniques and smart technologies (working on the basis of a special program) are being produced, and wide opportunities are being created for their practical use. And these are those who can thoroughly master the innovative methods and technologies produced for the continuous education system, have intellectual potential, and can consistently master the achievements of science and technology.

Solving such urgent and promising issues is currently considered a priority task by the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As proof of our opinion, the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 29, 2019 "On science and creative activity" ORQ-576 and "On Education" dated September 23, 2020 ORQ-637- and the laws of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 29, 2019 - Decree No. PF-5712 dated October "On Approving the Concept of Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" and No. PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019 "On Approving the Concept of Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", as well as

These cited state documents, on the one hand, set priorities for the development of science and technology and target resources; striving for science and creating an atmosphere of its attractiveness, attracting young people to scientific activity, training young talents; on the other hand, on the other hand, to raise the content of higher education to a new level in terms of quality, to fulfill the tasks of establishing a system of training highly qualified personnel who can contribute to the sustainable development of the social sphere and economic sectors, and who can find their place in the labor market. issues are in the main attention.

Such tasks of state importance have been defined as tasks that ensure the penetration of the third Renaissance of New Uzbekistan. That is why mature personnel with many innovative and developed intellectual potentials are needed now.

Solving these tasks, that is, preparing competitive mature personnel, is now important on a global scale, and many foreign scientists are engaged in such intellectual and creative activities. They are found in the following directions: on the intellectualization of education and its educational foundations in the works of foreign scientists (Yin J. et al [26], Toody GM, Mathur A [27] and others); on intellectualized teaching systems (L.N. Alesheva [6], V.M. Rembach [16], Yu.B. Popov [14] and others); significant scientific research work is being carried out on the intellectualization of interactive technologies and the preparation of virtual materials suitable for them (V.V. Golonkov [12], M.S. Artyukhina [7], etc.).

Important work is being done in our country to find effective and practical solutions to this problem. For example, U.Sh. Begimkulov [8], T.F. Bekmuratov [9], O.J. Bobomurodov [10], I. Boynazarov [11], Z.T. Rakhimov [15], O.Kh. Torakulov [21], M.Shamsiev [22], Sh.S.Sharipov [23], D.Yunusova [24], etc., significant work is being done on intellectualized education systems, preparation of future specialists for intellectual activity. This should be noted, as evidence for our opinions, we cite the opinions of a group of scientists below:

"In modern conditions, the main demand for the educational system is placed on the individual of the learner. His interests, needs, abilities, motivations should be taken into more consideration in the design of training and independent work processes.

The modern state of organization of educational processes is characterized by a number of features:

- rational selection of educational content, taking into account the needs of the person, his individual characteristics, development of criteria, methods and principles in this regard;
- standardization of organizational form and teaching methods and improvement of pedagogical processes in case of individualization of education requires a lot of work; researching ways of designing educational systems aimed at improving students' independent work in developing solutions to problems in this regard;
- the development of pedagogical and information technology integrations for the individual, which increases the relevance of developing the pedagogical foundations of the design of intellectual systems" [23, (26-27)].

So, in front of the problem of preparing future specialists to acquire intellectual knowledge, in the organization of educational processes, there is also the issue of developing and improving the professional and creative abilities of students related to the ability to analyze the possibilities of various intellectual systems and testing the use of innovative methods and technologies created on their basis in specific scientific fields. It follows from this that it is necessary to solve the problem of designing an intellectual system of education.

For this reason, in this article, we aimed to highlight the solution to the problem of forming an intellectual system of learning that raises the training of future specialists to a new level of quality. will be possible.

In this regard, significant work is being done in our country, i.e., the educational process of improving the quality of higher education, modernizing the personnel training system is being integrated with the latest achievements of science and technology, and as a result, a solid foundation is being prepared for the training of innovative and advanced mature personnel. On the basis of these, quality changes in the field of education for training future specialists and achieving high efficiency, their compatibility with the requirements of world education, and to what extent they find their place in practical and professional life are determined.

Naturally, the training of innovative, developed and competitive modern mature personnel cannot be carried out with traditional methods or technologies, that is, the transition period has come to abandon the "Teacher-textbook-student" paradigm in the training of future specialists and to the "student-textbook-teacher" paradigm.

We can cite the following reasons for this, namely, firstly, in the previous educational paradigm, the student was satisfied only with the knowledge given by the teacher through the textbook, secondly, more responsibility was assigned to the teacher, and thirdly, the specialist mainly acquired practical knowledge, skills and qualifications in the higher educational institution. - were directed to professional activities, fourthly, there was almost no need for additional research for the future specialist during his studies at the institution of higher education, fifthly, there was no special mass (for everyone) demand for the future specialist to engage in separate creative activities, sixthly, "student-textbook-teacher" educational paradigm places more responsibility on the learner, seventhly, in which the learner is forced to engage in more research, eighthly, the learner learns to search for materials related to the studied source and to extract from them the materials related to the study of the subject, ninthly, the learner learns how to use the extracted materials in the study of the subject - this is a unique creative process, tenthly, the most important, the learner is able to conduct independent work and learn to read independently.

If five of these reasons are eliminated and the training of future specialists is achieved by following the five, the training of innovative, advanced, competitive, and modern mature personnel will be achieved.

Also, the "student-textbook-teacher" educational paradigm itself is part of the intellectual systems of learning.

As you know, intellect is a Latin word that usually means intelligence, understanding, comprehension, understanding. In this sense, we can say that intelligence is the result of a person's ability to think in the expansion of his worldview. We can say that the intellectual system in this direction consists of the system of intellectual and logical activity of solving problems with the help of knowledge formed on the basis of the intellectual property of a person.

So, in the "requirement-textbook-teacher" paradigm, it will be possible to organize an intellectual system of learning on the basis of intellect and intellectual systems. The following opinion of Professor Sh.S. Sharipov about the intellectual system of learning is important: "The intellectual system of learning is the means of providing information necessary for students' independent study, mutual information exchange, as well as software and programs aimed at the development of the higher education system on the basis of information and communication technologies. is a systematic-organizational complex that includes organizational-methodical support" [23].

Based on this source and the above-mentioned modern achievements of science and technology, it can be seen from the essence of educational paradigms that their educational system for training future specialists is fully compatible with the credit-module systems currently entering the higher education system of our country.

It is known that the composition of the credit module system consists of two necessary elements. They are called: study load and study results. Read load and read output have the following meanings.

Study load this is the time it takes for a student to complete all of the systematic reading exercises and activities aimed at achieving specific learning outcomes.

Study results it is the set of knowledge and skills that the student is expected to learn, understand and be able to do as a result of completing the curriculum" [25].

A learner can earn a certain number of credits in the subject being studied only if he fulfills the required elements of the study load and learning outcomes.

So, in the educational paradigm "student-textbook-teacher" and in the credit-module system, the learner operates according to the intellectual system of acquiring knowledge. In both of them, the main focus is on improving the educational activity of the future specialist.

Based on our research in this field, we can say that a number of achievements and advantages can be obtained in teaching according to this educational paradigm. Based on our research, we defined them as follows: first, the future specialist learns to search for materials on the subject; secondly, the future specialist learns to distinguish first-level, second-level, etc. from the collected materials, thirdly, he learns to acquire new knowledge on the subject, fourthly, he learns to use the newly learned knowledge in mastering the subject he is studying, i.e., he learns to apply new knowledge, fifthly, on the subject is able to organize independent work and learn about his/her own creative activity,

These are the main focuses of the "student-textbook-instructor" educational paradigm, which is the basic principle of teaching learners how to read.

As a conclusion in this part of our study, it can be noted that the activity of the intellectual system of education is leading both in the "student-textbook-teacher" educational paradigm and in the credit-module system.

Taking into account these notes, it will now be possible to think about the main goal of the intellectual system of education and the main tasks of the intellectual system of the teacher.

Below are our thoughts on them. The main goal of the intellectual system of education is to make future professionals conscious and creative about the profession they want to take up It is to prepare them to be able to work independently on the basis of content formation and to regularly improve the quality of education by using the professional intellectual potential of professors and teachers.

The main tasks of the intellectual system of education are as follows:

- ensuring the quality of independent work of future specialists;
- formation of the skills of rational (reasonable) use of educational and methodical resources in future specialists;
- arming future specialists with modular and project-based educational technologies;
- forming the skills of future specialists to collect information on the studied source, process it and transfer it to the necessary sources;
- training future specialists to prepare information on the source they are studying (science, topic, concept, rule, law, etc.) and arming them with the basic principles of information exchange in this process;
- to prepare software and methodical resources for independent work, independent reading that future specialists may encounter in their professional activities.

These stated main goals and tasks do not lose their importance in the "student-textbook-teacher" educational paradigm and in the credit-module system.

We found it appropriate to quote the following source about the practical importance of the intellectual system of education:

"Implementation of the intellectual system of education creates wide opportunities for increasing the quality of education based on individualization and differentiation of the educational process, integration of various forms of education, and ensures continuity of education. The uniqueness of the proposed solution lies in the universality of the educational material deployment platform, the mobility and flexibility of education, the ability to self-check knowledge, skills and abilities" [23].

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